

Intermittent Failure Dynamics Characterization

A. Correcher, E. García, F. Morant, E. Quiles, and L. Rodríguez

Abstract—Diagnosis of intermittent failures is relevant for productive processes which sustain a high level of maintenance caused by failures. Systems including electrical contacts suffer a considerable amount of intermittent failures which are usually not diagnosed. A characterisation of the failure dynamics may save unnecessary repairs and enable a better planning component substitution. This paper presents a new concept in failure diagnosis, the modelling of intermittent failure dynamics. It develops two methodologies for modelling intermittent failure dynamics and generating information for maintenance scheduling.

Index Terms— Failure diagnosis, intermittent failures, maintenance scheduling

ACRONYM¹

IF	Intermittent Failure
PF	Permanent Failure
FR	Failure Rate
PDF	Probability density function
CDF	Cumulative distribution function
PLC	Programmable logic controller
LS	Least squares algorithm
RLS	Recursive least squares algorithm
DF	Failure density
LST	Linear Substitution Time
OTR	Operations to Replacement
P_s	Pseudoperiod
$MTBF$	Mean time between failures
EST	Exponential substitution time

NOTATION

$FT_{(i)Fj}$	Failure times array, related to failure Fj and device “ i ”.
$[FT_{(i,1)Fj}, \dots, FT_{(i,n)Fj}]$	
$FRT_{(i)Fj}$	Failure recovery times array, related to failure Fj and device “ i ”.
$[FRT_{(i,1)Fj}, \dots, FRT_{(i,m)Fj}]$	
$f_{Fj}(t)$	Function describing the model of failure Fj
PFT_{Fj}	Permanent failure times array, related to failure Fj and device “ $i=1 \dots p$ ”.
$[PFT_{(1)Fj}, \dots, PFT_{(p)Fj}]$	
$M_{FT,Fj}$	Failure times matrix, related to failure Fj . Each row is a $FT_{(i)Fj}$
$T_{(i)Fj}$	Failure duration times array related to failure Fj and device “ i ”.
$[T_{(i,1)Fj}, \dots, T_{(i,n-1)Fj}]$	

Manuscript received September 9, 2011. A. Correcher, E. García, F. Morant, E. Quiles are with the Universidad Politécnica de Valencia. (e-mail: {ancorsal, egarciam, fmorant, equiles}@upv.es)

¹ Singular and plural of an acronym are always spelled the same.

CT	Current time
$DF_{CT,Fj}$	DF of failure Fj computed at time CT
C_T	
LST_{CT}	LST computed at time CT
OTR_{CT}	OTR computed at time CT
P_{sCT}	P_s computed at time CT
EST_{CT}	EST computed at time CT
t_w	Sampling period

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial maintenance is a key area in order to increase the productivity of any industrial process. Maintenance programs can be designed according to cost risk strategies (Khan et al. [19], Martorell et al. [21], and Tan et al. [31]) or according to manufacturer recommendations. Recent research efforts are oriented to preventive maintenance strategies (see You et al [35], Sheu and Chang [27], Doyen and Gaudoin [11]) to decrease the total number of failures and process unavailability time. Nevertheless, failures happen and their effects must be solved as soon as possible in order to avoid further problems including production shutdown.

Intermittent failures (IF) are one special case of failures. IF can be defined (see IEEE [15]) as “Failures of an item for a limited period of time, following which the item recovers its ability to perform its required function without being subjected to any external corrective action”, moreover “such failures are often recurrent.”

IF are difficult to diagnose and may cause a great disruption in industrial processes and maintenance operations. The diagnosis of an IF will raise a specific reparation routine, but when the operator analyzes the faulty device the failure could have disappeared (see Qi et al. [25], Sorensen et al. [29]). In this case, the faulty device will be reinstalled and it could fail again and again. Moreover, IF recover without any corrective action, therefore IF effects must be studied in order to decide if corrective maintenance is necessary or not.

IF occur in a number of fields and have been studied since the 1970’s. The first field interested in this kind of failures was digital electronics. Many research groups and firms that develop circuit-testing systems have continued the initial studies of Savir [26] who defines two kind of IF: stationary IF (e.g.: connection looses) and transient IF (e.g.: failures produced by electromagnetic interference as in Kehl and Rosenstiel [18]). However, the last ones are completely random and were not usually considered and only failures that always produce the same effects when they appear were studied. The diagnosis system presented by Savir [26] compared the digital circuit output with a reference model free of failures.

Sorensen et al. [29] presented a software tool used for the aircraft industry. Their work outlines the importance of taking into account IF in electronic devices because aging of devices will lead to IF as a prelude of a permanent failure (PF). IF due to connection problems have serious consequences over system reliability. This occurs because not repaired damaged units carry on injecting IF in the system. These failures can be detected in other systems, generating false alarms and needless reparations. These situations are due to unsuitable testing of IF, and often they are the main reason to consider that these electronic systems are “worn out”.

Most IF are related to gradual degradation of components or systems. For instance, evolution of connection failures is shown in figure 1 (see Correcher et al. [9] and Sorensen et al. [29]). When IF are in stage 1 of their development, they show themselves as small noise fluctuations. As the amplitude and duration of the fluctuations increase (stage 2), IF start to occur. The effects of IF are severe in stage 3.

Therefore, in many instances, the occurrence of IF in a device is a prelude of PF. In these cases, if IF can be detected, appropriate actions could be taken in order to minimise economic impact.

Other fields in which the importance of IF has been studied are aircraft industry (see Anderson and Aylward [2], and Bavuso et al. [4]) and processes industry (see Madden and Nolan [22], and Sun [30]).

Electric contacts is, without any doubt, the application area where IF diagnosis has attracted more attention being fretting corrosion the most studied phenomenon. Antler [3] stated that thermal or mechanical vibrations in the contacts cause fretting corrosion. Vibrations induce relative movements between the two parts of the contact causing contact resistance to increase. These changes in resistance are intermittent and provoke intermittent connection failures (Maul et al. [23]).

Correcher et al. [9][10] presented an IF diagnosis tool. This tool was able to diagnose the failure and recovery events in a system with IF. Other approaches to IF diagnosis (see Contant et al. [8], Jiang et al. [17], and Abreu and van Gemund [1]) do not consider IF dynamics. However, the existence of such dynamics is experimentally shown in the works of Sorensen [29], Correcher et al. [9] and in the destructive tests presented in this paper.

Because IF recover without any corrective action, IF diagnosis does not need to raise (necessarily) a corrective maintenance routine. Corrective actions must be taken when IF cause unacceptable system behaviour. It will be interesting to model IF dynamics so the diagnosis system could be able to predict the best time to replace or substitute damaged devices.

Recent studies related to this concept (see, Carr and Wang [7], Ghasemi et al. [12], Woo et al. [33], Nanda et al. [24] or Balakrishnan and Asadi [5]) focus on including component residual life prediction in the predictive maintenance system. The goal of residual life predictions based on IF dynamics is not avoiding failures, but predicting the time when the effects of the IF will be unacceptable.

Fig. 1. Connection IF evolution through device life.

Therefore, we can introduce the problem:

Definition 1. IF dynamics characterization problem.

Starting from a set of failure times $FT_{(i)F_j} = [FT_{(i,1)F_j}, FT_{(i,2)F_j}, \dots, FT_{(i,m)F_j}]$, and a set of recovery times $FRT_{(i)F_j} = [FRT_{(i,1)F_j}, FRT_{(i,2)F_j}, \dots, FRT_{(i,m)F_j}]$, related to the same IF (F_j), and the same device “ i ” compute a model $f_{F_j}(t)$ of the failure times.

This model of failure times represents the IF dynamics for a single device and it can be used to make predictions of failure evolution and component residual life.

Only stationary IF (see Savir [26]) will be studied in this paper because transient IF are completely random, so they do not have dynamics.

The first step in the problem solution will be statistical failure modeling. This approach will lead to a statistical model which needs destructive tests of components in order to be validated. Section II presents an IF probabilistic model based on real experimental data. This model will be able to estimate failure probability at any time. Next step will be an on-line model of the failure that must be able to estimate the best time to repair or substitute the faulty device without any previous test. Section III studies the evolution of IF during its on-line diagnosis and some parameters are presented in order to model IF dynamics. These parameters will be useful for predicting the residual life of the device. We study some diagnosability issues in section IV, and, finally we present some conclusions in section V.

II. IF MODELING AND IF DYNAMICS.

A. Probabilistic Modeling.

Failure rate (FR) curve is usually used to model PF in different components. When one device is replaced or repaired the failure time can be used to update the curve. If we have replaced m devices with failure F_j , then the curve is built with the permanent failure times array $PFT_{F_j} = [PFT_{(1)F_j}, PFT_{(2)F_j}, \dots, PFT_{(p)F_j}]$, where each failure time is associated to one of the m replaced devices ($m \geq p$). The number of failure data times can be lower than the number of devices when working with censored data (see Lemmis [20]).

Lu [36] argues that there are two main curve models. The bathtub curve and the four-phase roller coaster curve. In the bathtub curve model (figure 2), FR decreases during the debugging period of the device, FR is constant during the useful life of the device and FR is increasing at the end. Infant mortality can be reduced by using reliability testing programs.

Fig. 2. Bathtub curve.

Nevertheless companies try to reduce the amount of time used to develop new products and time used in reliability testing has been reduced. Under this assumption, the bathtub curve does not fit well the data. Lu [36] showed that in these cases four-phase roller coaster curves (figure 3) fit the data better than bathtub curves. Brombacher et al. [6] explain that the first phase represents products outside the specification that reach the customer, the second phase represent a sub-population of products failing far earlier than the main population, the third and the fourth phase have the same meaning as in the bathtub curve.

IF are slightly different because each device can fail more than once. The set of failure times can not be represented by an array of failure times for each device family. It is much more suitable to represent the failure times with an array for each single device, and sometimes with a failure times matrix for the device family.

$$M_{FT,F_j} = \begin{bmatrix} FT_{(1,1)F_j} & FT_{(2,1)F_j} & FT_{(3,1)F_j} & \dots & FT_{(p,1)F_j} \\ FT_{(1,2)F_j} & FT_{(2,2)F_j} & & & \dots \\ \dots & & FT_{(i,j)F_j} & & \\ \dots & & & & \\ FT_{(m,1)F_j} & FT_{(m,2)F_j} & \dots & & FT_{(p,m)F_j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $FT_{(i,k)F_j}$ stands for failure F_j , failure time “ k ” ($k=[1\dots p]$) in device “ i ” ($i=[1\dots m]$). This matrix can be built assuming that every device suffer the same number of failures. This fact will be false in general; nevertheless it is convenient to include more failure times in each device assuming that the last failure is a PF. In this case, any later time will be a failure time and the FR curve could be computed by using the last failure time of each device as an element of the PF times array. When the last failure of any device is not a PF, failure times can be represented by a set of failure times instead of a failure times matrix.

There are a number of probability distributions to model FR (see Leemis [20]). This paper uses Weibull distribution, one of the most used distributions in reliability and life cycle-testing (see Jensen [16] or Tsai-Hung Fan and Wan-Lun Wang [32]), because of its flexibility in modeling different FR.

The probability density function (PDF) and the cumulative distribution function (CDF) for the Weibull model are:

$$f(t) = \frac{\beta}{\eta - \gamma} \cdot \left[\frac{t - \gamma}{\eta - \gamma} \right]^{\beta-1} \cdot e^{-\left[\frac{t - \gamma}{\eta - \gamma} \right]^\beta} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Four-phase roller coaster curve.

$$F(t) = 1 - e^{-\left[\frac{t - \gamma}{\eta - \gamma} \right]^\beta} \quad (3)$$

where β is the shape parameter, η is the characteristic life and γ is the location parameter.

If the location parameter is assumed to be zero, then the distribution becomes the two-parameter Weibull:

$$f(t) = \frac{\beta}{\eta} \cdot \left[\frac{t}{\eta} \right]^{\beta-1} \cdot e^{-\left[\frac{t}{\eta} \right]^\beta} \quad (4)$$

$$F(t) = 1 - e^{-\left[\frac{t}{\eta} \right]^\beta} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) can be used to define the characteristic life. If $t = \eta$ then the characteristic life is the time at which 63.2% of the units will fail. When working with IF, the characteristic life will be the time at which 63.2% of the IF will occur before a PF, therefore, it will be an interesting indicator of the residual life of the device.

The IF Weibull model can be used to estimate the actual failure probability and for simulation purposes.

B. Failure modeling example.

The authors have used a prototype to perform destructive testing of relays. It is shown in figure 4. One hundred relays have been tested for ten thousand operations (manufacturer limit) or up to non recoverable failure (PF). Tests show that relays resist even more operations than the manufacturer limit because they have not registered any PF. Because no PF has been obtained the FR curve can not be built for the relay family under these experimental conditions. Nevertheless, relays suffer IF.

The configuration of the prototype reproduces an industrial application. A PLC generates the control commands for the relays. Manufacturer limit DC current is 10 amperes. Relays switch 24 DC volts over 66 ohms resistive loads, so controlled current is below manufacturer limit not putting relays to work outside their specifications. Time between operations was 100 milliseconds and overall duration of each experiment was 277.8 hours.

A diagnosis system compares the expected current with the sensed current, so it can diagnose failures in relays. Failure and recovery times are recorded in order to perform off-line analysis. The first analysis considered if failure times fit any probability distribution. Results are shown in table I.

Fig. 4. Relay testing prototype.

TABLE I

CORRELATION OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA WITH PROBABILITY FUNCTIONS.

Distribution	Correlation factor
Weibull	0.976
Exponential	*
Lognormal	0.892
Loglogistic	0.899
Weibull (3 parameters)	0.991
Exponential (2 parameters)	*
Lognormal (3 parameters)	0.973
Loglogistic (3 parameters)	0.959
Lower extreme value	0.979
Normal	0.974
Logistic	0.96

Table I shows that there are several distributions with correlation factor next to one, therefore, these distributions will fit the data. This is due to the exponential nature of the models. This paper will use the Weibull model (see Jensen [16], and Lemmis [20]).

Figure 5 shows the results of fitting the data to a Weibull distribution. In this figure, “Shape” is the shape parameter, “Thres” is the location parameter, “Mean” is the mean of the distribution, “STDev” is the standard deviation of the distribution, “Median” is the median of the distribution, “IQR” is the interquartile range, “Failure” is the number of failure times included, “AD” is the Anderson-Darling coefficient and “Correlation” is the Pearson correlation coefficient. IQR is the distance between percentile 75th and percentile 25th. IQR is essentially the range of the middle 50% of the data. Because it uses the middle 50%, IQR is not affected by outliers or extreme values.

Anderson-Darling statistic measures how well the data follow a particular distribution. The better the distribution fits the data, the smaller this statistic will be. Anderson-Darling statistic is calculated by using the weighted squared distance between the fitted line of the probability plot (based on the chosen distribution and using either maximum likelihood or least squares estimates) and the nonparametric step function. The calculation is weighted more heavily in the tails of the distribution. This coefficient has not a good value in the example, this fact occurs because the data does not fit the distribution in the tails.

Fig. 5. Experimental data weibull fitting.

Pearson's correlation reflects the degree of linear relationship between the variables. A value of 1.0 means a perfect fitting. The value of this statistic is good, because the data fit the distribution during the useful life of the relay.

At this point, an IF Weibull model can be computed. So, the failure probability through the useful life of the device can be computed. The more data of other similar relays fit the curve the better will be the model. The tests reveal a five percent deviation between the identified parameters for each relay.

Nevertheless, destructive tests are needed in order to compute the Weibull model. These data is difficult to obtain a priori or it will be not possible in any industrial process. Nevertheless, if an IF diagnosis system records failure times then the model could be built dynamically during the diagnosis process. The model will increase its precision with time.

Usefulness of a failure diagnosis characterization implies not only long time benefits but short time results. In order to obtain short time results it is necessary to predict residual life not only with historical data but with actual data. Thus, new analyses are needed (see next section).

III. TEMPORAL MODELING.

The main goal of IF dynamics characterization is the estimation of the residual life of a faulty device. This information could be used in preventive maintenance. This section presents a model of IF dynamics that can be computed with actual data, therefore, no previous destructive tests are needed to compute the model.

IF dynamics can be characterized with two complementary parameters, namely Temporal failure density and Pseudoperiod. The definition of these parameters allows their on-line computing and their use to predict future behavior of the faulty device.

Failure density and Pseudoperiod are computed from the IF time occurrence and failure duration (defined as the time difference between recovery and failure). For each device (“*i*”) and failure (F_j), two arrays are constructed: the failure times array ($FT_{(i)F_j}$) and the recovery times array ($FRT_{(i)F_j}$) (see definition 1), which include n failures and m recoveries. It is easy to compute the failure duration times array ($T_{(i)F_j} = [T_{(i,1)F_j}, \dots, T_{(i,n-1)F_j}]$), where $T_{(i,k)F_j} = FRT_{(i,k)F_j} - FT_{(i,k)F_j}$.

These arrays can be computed recursively and on-line considering a moving time window of a given duration (w).

A. Temporal failure density.

Temporal failure density (DF or density in the rest of the paper) is defined as the average time a particular failure is active within a sliding time window of duration w . DF computed at time C_T for failure F_j (DF_{CT,F_j}) is defined as:

$$DF_{CT,F_j} = \frac{\sum_{k=l}^{CNT} (T_{(i,k)F_j}) + T_A}{w} \quad (6)$$

where CNT is the number of failures inside the window, l stands for the index of the first failure detected inside the window $\{l: FT_{(i,l)F_j} > (C_T - w) \text{ and } FT_{(i,l-1)F_j} < (C_T - w)\}$ if exists, otherwise $l=CNT+1$, and T_A takes into account the duration of a failure occurred before C_T-w which continues active inside the window. Therefore:

$$T_A = FT_{(i,l-1)F_j} + T_{(i,l-1)F_j} - (C_T - w) \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) is valid only if T_A is positive, otherwise $T_A=0$, as this fact would indicate that the $(l-1)th$ failure time is completely outside the window.

In a real system, DF tends to increase with time; thus confirming the hypothesis that IF progressively damage the faulty device. Figures 6 and 7 show the density computed from experimental data and its filtered signal (low-pass fourth order Butterworth filter). Taking into account that operation of the relays must not be continuous, it is much more suitable to analyze the operations of the device instead of the time. A new operation is considered on a rising edge of a relay switching.

The rising characteristic of DF can be used to estimate the optimal time to repair or substitute the faulty device. A certain maximum density threshold can be defined as the limit for unacceptable behavior. Then, an adequate extrapolation model can be used to predict the number of operations the device is capable of carrying out before reaching the unacceptable

behavior limit. Obviously, the unacceptable density threshold should be defined specifically for each device, depending on its specific functionality and reliability requirements.

The simplest prediction model could be a linear DF increase. In this case, filtered DF could be fitted with classical techniques (see Graupe [13]) such as least squares (LS) or recursive least squares (RLS). DF curve includes three phases: DF increases slowly at the beginning. In a second phase, DF increases with a higher rate. The last phase shows a constant DF increasing rate. Therefore, a linear model does not seem to be suitable to fit the whole data set. Nevertheless, the smoothness of filtered DF allows linear model fitting of a small data set. LS applied to DF values included in the sliding window, or RLS with a forgotten factor can be used to fit a linear model (see Xiaosong et al. [34] or Huynh et al. [14]).

DF must be organized as an array containing the values of DF computed inside the window. The set of DF values included in the window (D_{F_j}) can be defined as: $D_{F_j} = [D_{(1)F_j}, \dots, D_{(p)F_j}]$ ($p=w/t_m$) $D_{(p)F_j} = DF_{CT,F_j}$ (equation 6).

The proposed linear model to fit D_{F_j} is:

$$DF_{CT,F_j} = m_{CT} \bullet CT + n_{CT} \quad (8)$$

where m_{CT} and n_{CT} stand for the slope and the intercept of the identified model at time CT .

If the unacceptable value for DF is D_0 , the time (t_{D_0}) when density D_0 will be reached is:

$$t_{D_0} = \frac{(D_0 - n_{CT})}{m_{CT}} \quad (9)$$

t_{D_0} is a prediction of the time when the faulty device should be replaced. This value is named Linear Substitution Time (LST) at time CT ($LST_{CT} = t_{D_0}$).

Fig. 6. Failure density. Window size is 10000 operations.

Fig. 7. Failure density. Window size is 100000 operations

Fig. 8. OTR_{CT} for an acceptable density threshold below 15%.

In addition, it is possible to define another parameter much more suitable for preventive maintenance, the Operations to Replacement (OTR) at time CT (OTR_{CT}). This parameter represents an estimation of the useful operations left on a device (the residual life), and can be computed as:

$$OTR_{CT} = LST_{CT} - CT \quad (10)$$

Obviously, only positive values of OTR_{CT} are meaningful, otherwise the corresponding OTR_{CT} is considered equal to zero.

Therefore, the failure characterization system will be able to predict the time when a device must be substituted in two stages. First of all, DF_{CT,F_j} will be computed and, from this value, LST_{CT} and OTR_{CT} will be predicted.

Figure 8 shows the evolution of OTR_{CT} obtained from experiments in figures 6 and 7. Figure 8 shows that the device should be replaced when reaching 5.2 million operations instead of the substitution time recommended by the manufacturer (10 million operations).

The validity of the proposed linear prediction model has been found suitable to be used with the experimental data obtained from the destructive tests on the relays used through the paper. However, this kind of model might not be adequate for other devices. For instance, if the density follows first order dynamics, LST_{CT} will predict an optimistic substitution time. In any case, when an adequate sliding window is chosen, LST_{CT} and OTR_{CT} time evolution reflect the underlying failure dynamics. This time evolution could be used to model systems which do not follow linear increase laws.

As mentioned before, the sliding window size should be appropriately chosen. Short windows will introduce high variability and noise in DF . In contrast long windows introduce a greater filtering effect, but they introduce high computational costs and might mask part of the failure underlying dynamics. Figures 6 and 7 show the effect of window size in the variability of the density. From calculations with a range of window sizes, it has been found that windows greater than 5000 operations include the same low frequency component, as shown in figures 6 and 7. Therefore, LST_{CT} and OTR_{CT} computed from window sizes greater than 5000 operations are identical.

B. Pseudoperiod.

DF can be used to predict the device substitution time, however it does not completely explain the dynamics of the IF. For instance, figure 9 shows two cases with exactly the same DF where the effects on the device are clearly different. The difference between the two behaviours can be modeled by the time difference between the occurrences of two consecutive failures. The time difference can be measured with a new parameter, the Pseudoperiod (Ps) at time CT for failure F_j (Ps_{CT,F_j}). Ps can be defined as the average time difference between failures inside a sliding window of a given duration (w), normalized by the number of failures:

$$Ps_{CT,F_j} = \frac{\sum_{l=h}^{l=k} FT_{(i,l+1)F_j} - FT_{(i,l)F_j}}{k-h+1} = \frac{FT_{(i,k)F_j} - FT_{(i,h)F_j}}{k-h+1} \quad (11)$$

where CT stands for the current time, $FT_{(i,l)F_j}$ is the l^{th} failure time for failure F_j and device “ i ”, and h and k are the first and last failure inside the window, respectively.

Ps is clearly a magnitude related to the mean time between failures ($MTBF$), it is commonly used to model reliability of repairable systems. Ps is a dynamic magnitude and, for a particular device, a Ps curve can be calculated. This curve can also be used to predict the substitution time of the device. Evolution of Ps (figure 10) shows a decrease towards a value close to zero. This dynamic behavior is consistent with the nature of IF (figure 1).

Figure 11 shows that Ps remains in the range 400 to 900 operations from 4 million operations onwards. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that, in average, the number of failures from the 4 millionth operation remains reasonably constant, but the average duration of each failure slowly increases with the number of operations, as the density in figure 6 shows.

As in section III.A, a Ps model could be useful to predict OTR of the device. The shape of Ps suggests its modeling with a linear or an exponential model. Models must be fitted with LS or RLS with forgetting factor (see Hu et al. [34] or Huynh et al. [14]) as in section III.A.

Fig. 9. IF with the same density but different dynamics.

Fig. 10. Pseudoperiod. Window size 100000 operations.

Fig. 11. Zoom in figure 10.

Fig. 12. OTR computed with Ps , window is 100000 operations, $Ps_0=600$ operations.

Therefore, Ps must be arranged in an array (Ps_{Fj}) in order to fit a model to this array. $Ps_{Fj}=[Ps_{(1),Fj}, \dots, Ps_{(p),Fj}]$ ($p=w/t_m$) $Ps_{(p),Fj}=Ps_{CT,Fj}$ (equation 11). A linear model can be used to predict a LST (as in section III.A). An exponential model can also be used to predict substitution time.

$$Ps_{CT,Fj} = A \bullet e^{B \bullet CT} \quad (12)$$

If the unacceptable value for Ps is Ps_0 , then the model will predict the time to reach this threshold, t_{Ps_0} :

$$t_{Ps_0} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{Ps_0}{A}\right)}{B} \quad (13)$$

This value is named exponential substitution time (EST) at time CT ($EST_{CT}=t_{Ps_0}$). EST can be used to compute the residual life (OTR):

$$OTR_{CT} = EST_{CT} - CT \quad (14)$$

Figure 12 shows OTR computed with LST_{CT} (dashed line) and with EST_{CT} (continuous line) ($Ps_0 = 600$ operations.). Figure 12 shows that LST_{CT} is much more conservative than EST_{CT} . That is because the model is better represented by an exponential model. EST_{CT} predicts a substitution time of 4.65 million operations meanwhile LST_{CT} predicts 2.74 million.

C. Integrated model.

Previous sections have presented two main characteristics of an IF, DF and Ps . The complete modeling of the IF dynamics must include both characteristics. Moreover, the model is not only useful to characterize the IF but it can be used to predict the best time to substitute the device. The algorithm to compute the model can be summarized as:

Algorithm 1. On-line IF characterization.

- 1) At time CT . (window size is w and sampling period is t_m)
- 2) Update $FT_{(i)Fj}=[FT_{(i,1)Fj}, FT_{(i,2)Fj}, \dots, FT_{(i,n)Fj}]$ and $FRT_{(i)Fj}=[FRT_{(i,1)Fj}, FRT_{(i,2)Fj}, \dots, FRT_{(i,m)Fj}]$, remove any failure or recovery time lower than $CT-w$.
 - a. There is no new failure or recovery. Go to 3).
 - b. There is a new failure or recovery diagnosis.
 - i. $FT_{(i,n+1)Fj}=CT$ or $FRT_{(i,m+1)Fj}=CT$
 - ii. Update $FT_{(i)Fj}$ or $FRT_{(i)Fj}$
 - iii. When a recovery is diagnosed, compute the failure duration and update the duration times array.
 - iv. Compute $DF_{CT,Fj}$ with (6) and (7).
 - v. Compute $Ps_{CT,Fj}$ with (11).
- 3) Update $D_{Fj}=[D_{(1)Fj}, \dots, D_{(p)Fj}]$ $D_{(p)Fj}=DF_{CT,Fj}$ and $Ps_{Fj}=[Ps_{(1),Fj}, \dots, Ps_{(p),Fj}]$ $Ps_{(p),Fj}=Ps_{CT,Fj}$ ($p=w/t_m$), remove the first value and add the new computed value.
- 4) Filter D_{Fj} and Ps_{Fj}
- 5) Fit D_{Fj} and Ps_{Fj} . Compute models in equations (8) and (12).

- 6) Compute OTR_{CT} for each model. Select the more restrictive as a prediction.
- 7) Return to 1.

Algorithm 1 can be computationally improved by using RLS instead of RL in step 5. In this case, D_{F_j} and Ps_{F_j} must not be built because each DF_{CT,F_j} and Ps_{CT,F_j} are included directly in the algorithm. In order to fit the model only with recent data, a forgetting factor must be used (see Hu et al. [34] or Huynh et al. [14]).

The algorithm has been tested with experimental data. Results are shown in figures 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, and 12. The mean computation time of the algorithm was 10.2 milliseconds (1.26 milliseconds, standard deviation) in an Intel Core Quad 2.4 GHz (2 GB RAM).

IV. INTERMITTENT FAILURE DYNAMICS DIAGNOSABILITY.

In the previous sections we have defined models for the characterization of IF dynamics. In order to be useful, these models should be able to diagnose the IF dynamics.

First of all, it is necessary to ascertain if the proposed dynamic model can be used to perform the complete failure diagnosis as per definition 1. To complete definition 1, a definition of failure dynamics diagnosis is introduced, based on the definition of discrete-time systems observability (see Smolensky [28]). “A discrete-time system is observable if a finite k exists such that knowledge of the outputs to $k-1$ is sufficient to determine the initial state of the system. “

Definition 2. IF dynamics diagnosis problem.

Given a failure times sequence, $FT_{(i)F_j}=[FT_{(i,1)F_j}, FT_{(i,2)F_j}, \dots, FT_{(i,n)F_j}]$, and a recovery times sequence $FRT_{(i)F_j}=[FRT_{(i,1)F_j}, FRT_{(i,2)F_j}, \dots, FRT_{(i,m)F_j}]$, compute the next value in FT_{F_j} if $m \geq n$ or the next value in FRT_{F_j} if $m < n$.

Definition 2 states that IF dynamics is diagnosable if the next failure or recovery time can be computed. The asynchronous and non deterministic nature of the IF implies that the IF dynamics diagnosis problem cannot be solved with deterministic precision. Therefore, we propose a relaxed definition.

Definition 3. Bounded IF dynamics diagnosis problem.

Given a failure times sequence, $FT_{(i)F_j}=[FT_{(i,1)F_j}, FT_{(i,2)F_j}, \dots, FT_{(i,n)F_j}]$, and a recovery times sequence $FRT_{(i)F_j}=[FRT_{(i,1)F_j},$

$FRT_{(i,2)F_j}, \dots, FRT_{(i,m)F_j}]$, compute the next value in FT_{F_j} if $m \geq n$ or the next value in FRT_{F_j} if $m < n$, with a bounded uncertainty.

A. Bounded IF dynamics diagnosis with DF_{CT,F_j} .

Let us suppose that a diagnosis system reports a failure times sequence, $FT_{(i)F_j}=[FT_{(i,1)F_j}, FT_{(i,2)F_j}, \dots, FT_{(i,n)F_j}]$, and a recovery times sequence $FRT_{(i)F_j}=[FRT_{(i,1)F_j}, FRT_{(i,2)F_j}, \dots, FRT_{(i,m)F_j}]$, until current time (CT). Therefore, DF_{CT,F_j} can be computed with equations (6) and (7).

Let us assume that $T_A=0$, therefore, the next event will be a failure. In this case, the problem in definition 3 will consist of computing the time of the next failure event. As historical data is known until CT , it is possible to compute a sequence of failure densities $D_{F_j}=[D_{(1)F_j}, \dots, D_{(p)F_j}]$ ($p=w/t_m$). As discussed in section III, D_{F_j} can be fitted to a linear model, so, the estimated density for a given instant of time τ will be $D_{\tau F_j}=m_{CT} \bullet \tau + n_{CT}$, where m and n are the results of the LS (or RLS) estimation (see section III.A).

When there is a new failure in the system, density is increased, for a maximum of t_m/w , where t_m is the sampling period and w is the window size. Next failure will occur when the lineal model will estimate this new density value.

$$D_{CT,F_j} + \frac{t_m}{w} = m_{CT} \bullet FT_{(i,n+1)F_j} + n_{CT} \quad (15)$$

so

$$FT_{(i,n+1)F_j} = \frac{w \bullet (D_{CT,F_j} - n_{CT}) + t_m}{w \bullet m_{CT}} \quad (16)$$

The estimation error is, therefore, the error in the RLS fit (see Smolensky et al., [28]). If we want to compute the time to recovery, ($T_A \neq 0$) density will decrease in, at least, t_m/w , so:

$$FRT_{(i,m+1)F_j} = \frac{w \bullet (D_{CT,F_j} - n_{CT}) - t_m}{w \bullet m_{CT}} \quad (17)$$

Equation 16 has been tested over experimental data collected from a relay. At each time (CT) next failure time can be predicted, this result can be compared with next real failure time ($FT_{(i,n+1)F_j}$). The result is better represented by the percentage prediction error related to the real failure at current time ($\%PE_{CT}$):

$$\%PE_{CT} = \frac{FT_{(i,n+1)F_j} - \frac{w \bullet (D_{CT,F_j} - n_{CT}) + t_m}{w \bullet m_{CT}}}{FT_{(i,n+1)F_j}} \quad (18)$$

Fig. 13. Percentage prediction error in a relay.

Results are shown in figure 13. It is shown that prediction error is bounded. Moreover, figure 13 shows three phases in the curve: In the first phase, error remains bounded but it oscillates because the failure times array includes few data, so RLS density estimation error is high. At the second phase, the error raises (in absolute value) from 2.5 million to 4.5 million operations. This result is explained by the changes in the density curve. In this interval, RLS DF estimation algorithm must adapt the slope to the new shape, therefore the error raises until this process is concluded. The third phase lasts until the end. The error value is low (less than 9%) because the failure times array size is high, so RLS DF estimation error is low, and the shape of DF curve is stable.

We can conclude that DF diagnoses the IF dynamics with a bounded error.

B. Bounded IF dynamics diagnosis with statistic methods.

Section II shows a probabilistic characterization of IF by means of a Weibull distribution. Therefore, the problem in definition 3 can be treated as a probabilistic estimation problem such as "Compute the probability of failure before a time τ ".

If we assume that the failure times are Weibull distributed the probability is the CDF (see Lemis [20]):

$$P(FT_{(i,j)Fj} < \tau) = F(\tau) = 1 - e^{-\left[\frac{\tau-\gamma}{\eta-\gamma}\right]^\beta} \quad (18)$$

where β , η and γ have the same meaning as in equation (3).

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the problem of characterizing IF dynamics. The authors have presented two ways of modelling IF dynamics and they have tested them with experimental data. On one hand, the probabilistic model allows computing IF probability at any time. On the other, the temporal model allows on-line prediction of the best time to repair or substitute the faulty device. The first model is useful when having historical data. Nevertheless these data is difficult to obtain, so the temporal model is much more useful in general because it does not need these data.

The temporal model explains two main characteristics of an IF: IF duration increases over time and it happens more and more frequently. DF and Ps measure these characteristics.

This paper has also presented an algorithm to compute both parameters that is also able to predict OTR . OTR is a working deadline for the device, but its computing needs the definition of maximum desirable values for DF and Ps . These limits must be set by system expert. Running time of the algorithm restricts its use to systems with sampling time lesser than 15.24 milliseconds. Nevertheless, the algorithm could be used with faster systems if its computing is restricted. The algorithm can be executed (filtering, fitting and prediction) each 10000 operations (for example) and the result will not change because the dynamics of DF and Ps is slow.

The temporal model presents the problem of defining the sliding window size. Although it seems to be a complex problem, this paper has shown that, after filtering the data, the sliding window size has no impact over the predictions. Anyway, the window size can be dynamically changed and it can be adjusted during online monitoring of the device.

The main drawback of the approach is the definition of the maximum desirable values for DF and Ps . Future work will address this problem by exploring the interactions between control strategies and components IF.

This paper has also stated new definitions for IF dynamics and it has been proved that both models are able to diagnose IF dynamics.

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Antonio Correcher is an Assistant Professor of the Department of Systems Engineering and Control at Universitat Politècnica de Valencia, Spain (UPV). He received the B.S. degree in automatic control and electronic engineering from UPV, in 2001, and the PhD from the same University in 2006. His research interests include discrete event systems, hybrid systems and failure diagnosis.

Emilio García is an Associate Professor of the Department of Systems Engineering and Control at UPV. He received the Technical Engineering degree in 1988 from UPV, the Electronic Engineering degree in 1995 from Universitat de València (UV) and the Ph.D. degree in 2000 from UPV. His research interests cover discrete-event and hybrid systems control, fault diagnosis and predictive supervision and applications in marine current and wind power generation.

Francisco Morant is a Professor of the Department of Systems Engineering and Control at UPV. He received the Technical Engineering degree in 1976, the Industrial Engineering degree in 1982, and the Ph.D. degree in 1985 all from UPV. His research interests cover Intelligent Control Systems, and Fault Diagnosis of Complex Systems. In the last 20 years he has participate in several international research cooperation projects.

Eduardo Quiles is an Associate Professor of the Department of Systems Engineering and Control at UPV. He received the MSc degree in Electrical Engineering from UPV in 1993 and the PhD degree from the same University in 1998. His research areas are Fault Detection and Diagnosis and Power Distribution System Reliability.

Leonardo Rodríguez is a PhD candidate in the University Institute of Control Systems and Industrial Computing, UPV. He received the B.S. degree in Mechatronic Engineering from Universidad San Buenaventura, Bogota (USB) in 2003, the B.S. degree in Automation and Industrial Electronics Engineering from UPV in 2008 and the MSc. degree in 2008 from UPV. His research interests cover industrial automation, renewable energy systems, control of discrete event systems, Petri nets, hybrid systems, fault diagnosis and recovery and condition monitoring.